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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collEctions
through al and Virtual Experiences**

D1.2 Data Management Plan

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9	HOVERLAY	Hoverlay US	USA
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Executive summary

Deliverable **D1.2 (v3.0)** is the **third and final** version of the **PERCEIVE Data Management Plan**, produced under **WP1 / Task T1.5 (Data Management)** and submitted at **M36** as the consolidated “living document” that governed data handling throughout the project lifecycle. It aligns with the **Horizon Europe DMP template** and establishes consistent consortium-wide practices to ensure that PERCEIVE data and research outputs are managed according to **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles, while respecting **legal, ethical, security, and commercial constraints**. It is based on the **HORIZON EUROPE Data Management Plan Template Version 2.0¹** and other sources such as the Data Documentation Initiative.

The DMP has two main functions:

1. **Inventory and governance:** provide an overview of the heterogeneous datasets and outputs generated/used by PERCEIVE (including **imaging, analytical, semantic, 3D, synthetic, and user-study data**) and define policies for processing, sharing, and long-term preservation.
2. **Compliance framework:** define guidelines, mechanisms, and tools for **personal data protection**, privacy, and ethical aspects—especially relevant for **user studies and participatory activities**—with explicit commitment to **GDPR compliance** and responsible research.

The DMP describes the strategic decisions made to manage the data generated and/or handled by the PERCEIVE consortium during the project, including decisions to make this data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The DMP is a living document that has been updated periodically as the project progresses.

The first draft of this report was due in M6. The report is intended for the 11 partner organizations participating in the PERCEIVE project from EU and Associated countries. The purpose of the report was to establish consistent practices for data handling among partners, which eventually increased the efficiency and reliability of the project's data delivery.

This Deliverable provides the third and final update of the DMP, following the version submitted at M06. As a living document, the DMP has been periodically refined to reflect the evolution of the PERCEIVE project, consolidating all strategic decisions on how the diverse data generated and/or managed by the PERCEIVE consortium (including imaging, analytical, semantic, 3D, synthetic and user-study data) are made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR), while respecting legal, ethical, security and commercial constraints, as well as the project's Open Science policy.

The intended audience for this report is internal: the 11 partnered organisations participating in PERCEIVE from 9 EU & Associated countries. The DMP establishes consistent practices between partners to increase the efficiency and robustness of data handling during the delivery of the project. PERCEIVE has been fully committed to the principles of responsible science that includes research ethics, data management compliance with the open science and FAIR principles, gender equality and non-discrimination and the implementation of GDPR requirements. WP1, as of which this deliverable has been elaborated, improved awareness of these principles among the partners and stakeholders and ensured that all principles were properly addressed.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan-annotated_en.pdf

Document History

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V0.4	28/07/2023	Final Version Released	CNR
V0.5	25/07/2025	Second Iteration on DMP, File storage and usage added	Fraunhofer
V0.6	14/11/2025	Asset tables collecting data extended	Fraunhofer, All
V0.7	10/01/2026	Third Iteration on DMP, Overview of Assets, FAIR mechanism updated	Fraunhofer
V0.8	17/01/2026	Finalising table overview	Fraunhofer, All
V0.9	23/01/2026	Ethics section added and reviewed	Fraunhofer, CNR
V1.0	30/01/2026	Review of final document	CNR

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Introduction

This deliverable presents the third and final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the PERCEIVE project. The DMP is produced under Task T1.5 “Data Management”, within Work Package WP1 “MANAGE: Administrative and Technical Project Management”. The first and second versions of the DMP were submitted to the European Commission at M06 and M24 respectively and have been continuously refined during the project lifecycle. At M36, this updated and final version is submitted as an update to Deliverable D1.2.

The DMP has a twofold objective. First, it provides an overview of the datasets and research outputs that partners collected and generated throughout PERCEIVE (including imaging, analytical, semantic, 3D, synthetic, and user-study data), and sets out the main policies for their management, processing, sharing and long-term preservation in line with FAIR and Open Science principles. Second, it defines guidelines, mechanisms and tools for partners regarding personal data protection, privacy and ethical aspects, in particular in view of user studies and participatory activities.

PERCEIVE’s overarching ambition is to reshape the way, colored Cultural Heritage collections and digital artworks are perceived, preserved, curated, exhibited and accessed. The project aimed to:

- (1) make heritage science results immediately usable by creative industries;
- (2) improve museums’ digital curatorial and exhibition practices for fragile colored collections;
- (3) advance AI-based methods for realistic color reconstruction, light transfer and color change prediction;
- (4) widen access and engagement through meaningful on-site and remote VR/AR/MR experiences grounded in “care”, “authenticity” and “accessibility”; and
- (5) foster citizens’ re-appropriation of colored collections by nurturing a concrete “sense of care” for their fragility and diversity.

The DMP consolidates all strategic decisions on how PERCEIVE data will support these objectives while complying with legal, ethical, security and commercial constraints.

Data Summary

The data for PERCEIVE comes from various sources, and many of the project's work packages are expected to generate data. The DoA section provides a summary of the outputs that will be generated during the project to better understand the information provided in this document.

The data collected, generated and used in PERCEIVE, include primary or processed and interpreted data created by research activities carried out in the framework of the project. It includes all stages of data creation and processing, along with all the metadata required to identify, validate and potentially re-use the data.

However, the notion of “PERCEIVE data” also covers a wider range of digital assets, including publications, reports, survey data, documentation, multimedia material and software. Figure 1 represents an architecture of different layers of data creation and the general dataflow through the several PERCEIVE creation, processing, interpretation, or generation processes used in the project.

Figure 1. PERCEIVE Dataflow. A general scheme that outlines processes, input data and output data, at different layers of a general architecture adopted by PERCEIVE.

Data management practices following FAIR principles, as defined in this document, will be incorporated into the general PERCEIVE dataflow as represented in Figure 1. This involves ensuring data quality, data governance, data security, and data lifecycle management, determining how data is stored, organized, accessed, and secured at each layer.

Since the Data Management Plan is a living document, all tables in the document will be updated throughout the project's duration.

A full list of PERCEIVE data will be generated during the project and appended to the final version of this DMP (Data Summary section). All the data that will be created in the Project, either new or as a derivative of existing data, will be considered as PERCEIVE results and, being part of PERCEIVE Knowledge base, will be made accessible following FAIR principles. However, the meaning and context of this new data will often rely on supporting Background Data (As Background is considered data, know-how, information or rights that exists before the GA is signed and that is needed to implement the project's actions or to exploit its results. Background Data, such as the metadata describing and identifying the heritage objects that will be studied, or supplementary information that

supports or adds context to the datasets that will be generated in the project will also need to be published to ensure that any generated results can be fully usable and exploitable. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data ownership issues are addressed in the GA and this document is intended to only address the aspects related to “access to” and “use of” PERCEIVE Data.

PERCEIVE heavily relies on data to achieve its anticipated outcomes, and most work packages were expected to generate relevant research data. The large amount of data expected is due to the number of institutions and pilots collaborating on developing the different suites. A key ambition of PERCEIVE is to support the European data ecosystem by making as many open access datasets as possible. The open access data generated by PERCEIVE will be a valuable resource for researchers and museums in the cultural heritage ecosystem.

For WG2 on paintings scenario the data to be used in the project (according to the data workflow proposed by WP3) was previously generated in analytical campaigns and research projects (e.g., MOLAB or MFT workshops) or have been acquired internally by museum through photographic or multispectral techniques (where the case, e.g., Scream analogic and digital pictures). The amount of data still needs to be assessed but probably overpasses Gb size (less than 1 terabyte).

FAIR Data

The FAIR data concept aims to increase the value of data by making it easily discoverable, accessible, usable, and interoperable for future projects and research. This requires a holistic and systemic approach to data management, which prioritizes openness while also respecting the need for restrictions when necessary. The principles of FAIR data apply to all research data, including the datasets generated in the project's innovation activities by the partners.

To adhere to these principles, the PERCEIVE project will store its open access research data and results in Zenodo, a service funded by the European Commission and maintained by CERN, which is integrated into the European Open Science Cloud.

Making data findable

To ensure easy identification and distinction of datasets, each one is assigned a unique name. This name can also serve as the dataset identifier. To create these names, PERCEIVE employs the following approach: each dataset name consists of four distinct parts, separated by an underscore character '_':

Format: **PERCEIVE_[Dataset Id] [Dataset Title]-[Nature]_[Project Month]**, where:

1. The dataset title is a descriptive name for the dataset, with no separation between words and the first character of each word in upper case.
2. The version number indicates any previous iteration of the dataset, with ordinal numbers used for major changes, decimal numbers for minor changes, and a lowercase 'v' for versions.
3. The project month represents the month of the project lifecycle when the dataset was generated, using single-digit numbers (e.g., M01 for the first month).

For example, a dataset named "First Test Samples" in its second version, generated at the sixth month of the project, would be named **PERCEIVE_FirstTestSamples_v2_M06**.

The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is a unique identifier assigned to research publications by most publishers to facilitate citation and discoverability. Zenodo, a service funded by the European Commission and maintained by CERN, automatically generates a DOI for any open access documentation uploaded to the platform. This improved findability of all project resources.

Zenodo also provides version control and enriches uploaded data with metadata that complies with DataCite's Metadata Schema. Each uploaded element receives a mandatory Digital Object Identifier (DOI) at the top-level.

The PERCEIVE consortium has agreed to use the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative metadata standard for all published outputs. This standard may be extended with additional keywords and other relevant metadata specific to each dataset.

Title	The title of the document
Subject	The topic of the document
Description	Brief description of the document
Creator	Author of the document
Publisher	Partner responsible for publishing the document
Contributor	Partners that have contributed to the compilation of the document
Date	The date of publication of the document
Type	The type of document (scientific paper, opinion piece, etc.)
Format	File format of the document (pdf, word, etc.)
Identifier	Digital Object Identifier provided by Zenodo
Language	The language of the document
Rights	Information on who has rights on the document

Making data openly accessible

All open access outputs from the PERCEIVE project will be uploaded to the PERCEIVE Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/perceivehorizon/>). There is no limit on the size of communities, so long-term preservation costs are avoided. During the DOI registration process, the metadata of each record is sent to and indexed on DataCite servers, which are compatible with the Dublin Core Metadata Standard. To improve findability, the consortium will be asked to provide additional metadata and keywords beyond the initial metadata standard. A list of these metadata and keywords will be provided in future deliverables and maintained accordingly.

Archiving on Zenodo is free of charge, which eliminates any costs associated with it. Zenodo's terms and conditions specify that the uploader is responsible for ensuring that the content is suitable for open dissemination and complies with all applicable regulations, including data protection, privacy, and intellectual property laws. To ensure compliance with EU legal-ethical legislation, a specific review process will be implemented for Open Access uploads. All relevant stakeholders in PERCEIVE will be notified of this requirement and requested to act accordingly, which may include a process of anonymizing the uploaded contents.

Zenodo also provides version control and mandatory assignment of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each uploaded element. A DOI is automatically assigned to all Zenodo files, and version control is provided by Zenodo. DOI versioning is achieved by registering two DOIs for one record; one represents the specific version of the record, while the other represents all versions of the record. For example, if a software package has two versions, the DOIs will be as follows:

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- v1.0 (specific version): 12.3456/zenodo.7891
- v1.1 (specific version): 12.3456/zenodo.7892

Changes in the file metadata will not result in a new DOI.

Low-volume Closed Access outputs that need to be shared, as well as general documentation, has been stored on Microsoft SharePoint. This is because SharePoint provides robust encryption mechanisms and tools for enforcing access control policies, while also ensuring compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Figure 2: PERCEIVE's Zenodo repository

Other data acquired or required by the PERCEIVE solutions (e.g., sensor data or archives) that are not intended for Open Access will be stored in the respective partner's private infrastructure.

Making data interoperable

The project does not anticipate the use of specific vocabularies. Ontologies will be aligned to CIDOC-CRM that makes metadata available in a standardised way. This exclusively has been adopted by the knowledge repository, described in [PERCEIVE Colour Knowledge Repository - PERCEIVE](#). However, if the need arises, and it is feasible to do so, the PERCEIVE project will use community-endorsed open vocabularies (e.g., Getty Vocabularies, <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/index.html>). If uncommon or project-specific keywords or terms, vocabularies/ontologies are used to describe or define PERCEIVE data, they will be made publicly available if there is potential benefit to the scientific community. If any generated ontologies or vocabularies will not be made publicly available, the reasons for this decision will be clearly stated in future updates.

Increase Data Re-Use

The PERCEIVE project is committed to achieving data FAIRness and promoting open data. While some data generated may be confidential due to intellectual property rights, any data that does not harm the competitiveness of project partners will be published and permanently stored in the project's Zenodo community. Standard reuse licenses, as open Creative Commons licence, or an agreed equivalent licence, preferably CC-0 or CC-BY, will be used to encourage the use of the data by third parties from the moment of its release.

To improve the reusability of datasets, each dataset is accompanied by a description that contains all necessary information for understanding the file. The responsible project's data management ensured that data management policies have been consistently implemented throughout the project.

The long-term management of project outputs begins in the final month of the project. All Open Access outputs must be uploaded to a repository that adheres to European regulations and ensures long-term preservation. Backups of all Closed Access outputs will be kept for five years to comply with obligations and then deleted from all consortium repositories unless otherwise requested. Partners must also ensure that all relevant data from the project is stored in their own infrastructure by this time.

Other research outputs

The PERCEIVE project is actively managing and tracking other valuable outputs generated by the consortium partners, as well as those designated as open access. In addition to data in common formats such as Excel, CSV, JSON, and images in JPEG/PNG, the consortium has identified other types of outputs that can be categorized as "other outputs", including:

- Questionnaires
- Reports and analysis
- Open access publications
- Scripts

Allocation of Resources

The Data Management task is led by FORTH (D3.3). As a research organization specializing in data, FORTH has developed a workflow (see Figure 1) to effectively achieve the objectives of this task. FORTH's team involved in the project includes a Data Manager, who serves as the consortium's Focal Point for data management activities, and a legal-ethical expert, who will actively participate in the review process of open access outputs before their release. A Focal Point will be appointed for each organization, serving as the main point of communication between the Data Managers and each partner, ensuring that all policies are implemented.

No additional budget is required for the Data Management task beyond the personnel costs already allocated to this task:

- The consortium will use SharePoint to store and share low-volume datasets within the consortium, and the project coordinator (CNR) already has a license for this service. Documents will be preserved for five years after the project's end to comply with Grant Agreement requirements.
- For open access outputs, all releases will be published in Zenodo, which is free and preserves uploads indefinitely. The only limitation of Zenodo is a 50 GB limit per individual upload, which is not expected to be exceeded.

Data Security

During the Discovery & Planning Phase, data security procedures will be defined:

- At M06, an initial iteration of the data security provisions will be established.
- During the Initial Data Collection Phase these implementations will be tested.
- If any weaknesses are identified by the actors involved in the Data Management Plan, they will be addressed at the second iteration of the Discovery & Planning Phase.
- Any changes made will be incorporated into subsequent iterations of the Data Management Plan.

One of the key reasons for choosing SharePoint over other infrastructures is its advanced security features. As mentioned in the "Repository" subsection, SharePoint offers robust encryption mechanisms for both data at rest and in transit and is compliant with the GDPR. In the event of a data

breach, Microsoft will notify the administrators of CNR's IT department to ensure a quick response. Regular backups will also be made to ensure data recovery in case of any unexpected data loss.

PERCEIVE Data Summary

A full list of PERCEIVE data will be generated during the project and appended to the final version of this DMP. The following table presents an overview of the general assets that have been processed during the lifecycle of the project:

Output Title DATASET	Access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - XRF mapping data, providing elemental distribution	Closed access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - colorimetry data	Closed Access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	Closed Access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) data	Closed Access
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - digital microscopy data	Closed Access
V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954) - XRF mapping data, providing elemental distribution	Closed Access
V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954) - colorimetry data	Closed Access
V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954) - Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) data	Closed Access
V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954) - Digital microscopy	Closed Access
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - Photogrammetry	Closed Access
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - colorimetry data	Closed Access
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	Closed Access
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - colorimetry data	Closed Access
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	Closed Access
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - Photogrammetry	Closed Access
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - colorimetry data	Closed Access
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	Closed Access
Mock-ups of V&A Dress - colorimetry data	Closed Access
Mock-ups of V&A Dress - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	Closed Access
Harold Taylor collection of autochromes (Maintainer Fraunhofer)	Closed Access
Mock-ups of polychromy - Multiangle reflectance data	Open Access
Mock-ups of polychromy - Material Exchange file	Open Access
Mock-ups of polychromy - Blender asset file	Open Access
6298_HighPoly	Closed Access
6298_GLTF_optimised	Closed Access
6298_UVL	Closed Access
6298_VIL	Closed Access
6928_Microscope	Closed Access
6298_XRF	Closed Access

6298_FORs	Closed Access
Isisi_with_sistro-output-gltf	Closed Access
Isisi_with_sistro-output-textures	Closed Access
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-packed	Closed Access
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-obj	Closed Access
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-obj	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 1_Video Intro_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 2_Video Ricostruzione_20250905_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 3_Video Transizione_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 4_Video Task A-_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 5_Video Task B_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 6_Video Task C_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 7_Video Rito finale_20250904_EN	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskA_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskA_9-16	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskB_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskB_9-16	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskC_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskC_9-16	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Architetto_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Architetto_9-16	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Pittrice_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Pittrice_9-16	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Scultore_16-9	Closed Access
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Scultore_9-16	Closed Access
1_18 (Base with gorgoneion between sphinx) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_25 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_26 (Illustratio with situla holder priest) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_27 (Architectural view with painting with landscape, complete with base) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_28 (Illustration with landscape) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_29 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia, complete with base) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_30 (Illustration with priest holding an oil lamp) - photoplane	Closed Access
1_31 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	Closed Access

It is worth noting that dissemination and communication outputs—such as scientific and community driven publications, Open Science and outreach materials, and related content—are not listed here. In line with PERCEIVE’s objectives to make heritage science results accessible and to widen engagement of museums, creative industries and citizens, these outputs are reported in the corresponding WP8 dissemination and exploitation deliverables and recorded in the Grant Management System. All Open Access outputs are made publicly available via appropriate repositories (e.g. a PERCEIVE community on Zenodo or institutional archives), ensuring longterm, FAIR access.

Publication and Sharing

The publication and sharing phases were scheduled at M18, M24, M30 and M36. In each of these periods, all Open Access (OA) outputs that have been collected and internally reviewed are deposited in suitable repositories (e.g. a PERCEIVE community on Zenodo and/or trusted institutional or domain repositories) that provide infrastructures aligned with the FAIR principles. In line with PERCEIVE's Open Science policy and its objectives to make heritage-science results reusable by museums, creative industries and citizens, additional repositories are also explored whenever they can increase the visibility and impact of specific research outputs (e.g. datasets, software, experience prototypes).

By M36, all planned OA releases are prepared and quality-checked before publication. In accordance with the commitments in the PERCEIVE DoA, the project aimed to provide at least one OA dataset per Work Package and, in practice, to associate OA datasets with the main PERCEIVE tools, services and experience prototypes (e.g. imaging and analytical data, semantic resources, 3D and synthetic data, user-study datasets).

As indicated above, dissemination and communication outputs—such as scientific and community driven publications, Open Science and outreach materials, and related content—are not included in this dataset count, as they are reported in the corresponding WP8 dissemination and exploitation deliverables and recorded in the Grant Management System. When these D&C materials are also taken into account, the overall volume of publicly available OA outputs produced by PERCEIVE is substantially higher, further supporting the project's aims of accessibility, engagement and citizens' re-appropriation of colored Cultural Heritage collections.

Open Science Strategy and PERCEIVE Data Handling

Within PERCEIVE's data handling and Open Science strategy, [Perceive Horizon | Zotero](#) is used as a shared reference management environment to support transparent, well-documented and reusable research. It helps partners collect, organise, annotate, cite and share bibliographic and documentary sources (e.g. scientific papers, standards, protocols, project reports, other publications) that are linked to datasets, software and experience prototypes described in the DMP.

Key roles of Zotero for PERCEIVE:

- **Reference collection:** Captures citation information from digital libraries, museum catalogues and databases relevant to heritage science, AI, imaging and XR.
- **Structured organisation:** Allows references to be grouped by work package, scenario, dataset or prototype, and tagged with controlled keywords, supporting traceability and DMP reporting.
- **Document handling:** Stores and annotates PDFs and other files (e.g. methodological guidelines, policy documents) that document data acquisition, processing and analysis workflows.
- **Consistent citation:** Integrates with word processors (Word, Google Docs, LibreOffice) to generate consistent citations and bibliographies in PERCEIVE deliverables, publications and training materials.
- **Collaboration & synchronisation:** Shared group libraries give all partners access to a common, always up-to-date corpus of references, aligned with PERCEIVE's FAIR and Open Science commitments.

Figure 3: PERCEIVE's Zotero entry

PERCEIVE PLATFORM AND Service-INFRASTRUCTURE

By M36, PERCEIVE has delivered the core services and building blocks that underpin its AI- and service-based architecture and support the project's objectives (OB1–OB5):

- PERCEIVE Platform and Toolkit Hub** A web-accessible platform that acts as a single entry point to PERCEIVE's tools and services for color reconstruction, prediction, light-damage estimation, 3D visualisation and experience prototyping. It is linked to the project website and the PERCEIVE Color Knowledge Repository and is designed to be deployable on institutional and/or trusted cloud infrastructures, in line with the project's Open Science and FAIR data commitments.
- PERCEIVE Color Knowledge Repository** A curated, FAIR-aligned repository (WP3) that stores raw, processed and synthetic color data (images, spectral and analytical data), 3D models and semantic/contextual information for all PERCEIVE scenarios (polychrome sculpture, paintings, textiles, photographs, born-digital AR artworks). It also consolidates the results of PERCEIVE's color reconstruction, prediction and light-damage studies. The repository serves as a shared knowledge base for museums, heritage scientists, creative industries, educators and citizens, and underpins reusable tools, services, APIs and training materials, directly supporting OB1–OB3.
- Integration and Interlinking Components** Components that interlink the PERCEIVE repository, APIs and experience prototypes, allowing color, material and contextual data to flow along the full pipeline: from acquisition and modelling (WP3–WP4) to tools and services (WP5) and then to visitor-facing experiences (WP6). This directly serves OB3–OB4, ensuring that reconstructed and predicted colors can be experienced in meaningful, "authentic" scenarios.
- Catalogue of PERCEIVE Tools, Services and Prototypes** A structured catalogue that exposes PERCEIVE tools, services, datasets and experience prototypes to the different stakeholder groups (museums, heritage scientists, creative industries, educators, citizens). It supports new business and engagement models (e.g. "authenticity-based" PERCEIVE Experiences), while keeping scientific provenance and documentation transparent.
- Evaluation, Logging and Analytics Framework (WP7)** A set of mechanisms and tools to capture anonymised usage data, user-study results and qualitative feedback across the

PERCEIVE prototypes (AUTHENTICITY, CARING, OPEN MUSEUM). This framework operationalises OB4 and OB5 by enabling the PERCEIVE Evaluation Toolkit and providing evidence of impact on understanding, engagement and “sense of care” (Ref. D7.1).

In line with PERCEIVE’s data management strategy and Open Science policy:

- All PERCEIVE nodes and services are hosted on secure, EU/EEA-based institutional or trusted cloud infrastructures; access to administrative functions is restricted to a small number of authorised technical staff from the relevant partners.
- Personal and sensitive data (e.g. from user studies) are processed under privacy-by-design and data-minimisation principles, kept logically separated from public research outputs, and handled in full compliance with GDPR and relevant national regulations.

Ethics & Other issues

The PERCEIVE project aims to minimize ethical and other issues within its workflow. To this end, a legal expert from FORTH will be available throughout the project's lifetime to provide advice and reviews, with a particular focus on outputs that will be shared outside of the consortium.

In the early stages of the project, the Data Management team has prioritized identifying potential ethical and other issues that may arise during the project. To this end, partners were asked to identify potential outputs to be generated and shared during the project, as well as any risks that needed to be considered. The consortium has identified the following key issues:

- **Ownership:** As the project involves multiple partners, ownership of outputs generated in collaboration with multiple partners is a potential issue that needs to be considered. The Data Managers will support a consensus among the partners involved and only intervene if the consortium requests it. This issue will be reviewed during subsequent plenary meetings.
- **Infrastructure:** If generated datasets are larger than expected, infrastructure may become an issue. In such cases, the Data Managers will make the necessary arrangements to address the issue.
- **Commercially sensitive information:** Some of the datasets generated by partners may contain commercially sensitive information that could prejudice commercial interests if shared outside of the consortium. To prevent this, access policies will be enforced on all closed-access outputs uploaded to the consortium's infrastructure, and open-access outputs will be reviewed before uploading to the Internet to avoid leaks.
- **Accuracy of generated data:** The output data of the consortium include predictions of color suggestions of past works of art. It is possible that the predictions are skew from reality and therefore depicting a false image of the past. This needs to be managed so that it is clear the predicted outputs are suggestions which were created with the data available, and that the consortium is not ethically liable for misrepresenting the past.

However, the consortium has proven its ability that these issues have been effectively managed and mitigated with appropriate planning and collaboration among all partners.

Summary Data Overview

Output Title: PERCEIVE_[Dataset Id] [Dataset Title]_[nature]_[Project Month]	Format	Volume (MB)	Owner Entity	Open/Closed Access	Actual Processing Date	Relevant Tasks
1_1 INV 8875(Base with griffon between dolphins) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	221	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_1 (Base with griffon between dolphins) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	60,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_10 INV 8539 (Architectural view with nilotic landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	551	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_10 (Architectural view with nilotic landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	121	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_11 INV 9425 (Illustration with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	250	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_11 (Illustration with landscape) - photoplane	.tif	19,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_12 INV 9128 (Pan with drum and basket for offerings) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	250	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_12 (Pan with drum and basket for offerings) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	17,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_13 INV 8884 (Dais with dolphins) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	223				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_13 (Dais with dolphins) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	19,2	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_14 INV 8695 (Painting with still-life) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	134				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_14 (Painting with still-life) - image	.tif	133	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_15 INV 94444 (Painting with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	182				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_15 (Painting with landscape) - image	.tif	29,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_16 INV 9932 (Edicola with lion) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	489				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_16 (Edicola with lion) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	39,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_17 INV 8542 (Base with gorgoneion between lioness) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	308				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_17 (Base with gorgoneion between lioness) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	129	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_18 INV 8874 (Base with gorgoneion between sphinx) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	309				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_18 (Base with gorgoneion between sphinx) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	67,8	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_19 INV 8543 (Base with marine dragon between dolphins) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	242	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_19 (Base with marine dragon between dolphins) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	60,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_2 INV 8607 (Architctural view with nilotic landascape and frieze) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1300	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_2 (Architctural view with nilotic landascape and frieze) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	351	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_20 (Architctural view with painting with naumachia) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	590	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_20 (Architctural view with painting with naumachia) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	186	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_21 (Illustration with priestess with sistro) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	82,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_21 (Illustration with priestess with sistro) - image	.tif	20,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_22 (Semi-panel and view with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1830	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_22 (Semi-panel and view with landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	192	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_24 (Semi-panel and view with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1830	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_24 (Semi-panel and view with landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	180	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_25 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	2210	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_25 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	265	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_26 (Illustratio with situla holder priest) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	373	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_26 (Illustratio with situla holder priest) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	48,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_27 (Architectural view with painting with landscape, complete with base) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	234	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_27 (Architectural view with painting with landscape, complete with base) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	41,2	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_28 (Illustration with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	208	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_28 (Illustration with landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	23,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_29 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia, complete with base) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	2000	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_29 (Architectural view with painting with naumachia, complete with base) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	150	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_3 (Architctural view with painting with still-life and frieze) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1110	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_3 (Architctural view with painting with still-life and frieze) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	336	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_30 (Illustration with priest holding an oil lamp) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	225	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_30 (Illustration with priest holding an oil lamp) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	31,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_31 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	2160	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_31 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	304	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_32 (Peacocks on garlands) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	84,5				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_32 (Peacocks on garlands) - image	.tif	13,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_33 (Painting with still-life) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	250				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_33 (Painting with still-life) - image	.tif + .tfw	16,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_34 (Base with marine griffon between dolphins) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	206				T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_34 (Base with marine griffon between dolphins) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	116	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_35 (Architectural view with painting with still-life) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	501	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_35 (Architectural view with painting with still-life) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	107	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_36 (Illustration with priestess with mask of Anubi) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	84,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_36 (Illustration with priestess with mask of Anubi) - image	.tif	94,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_37 (Upper part of th epanel surmounted by the frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	980	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_37 (Upper part of th epanel surmounted by the frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	153	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_38 (Illustration with priest with priest with pal branch) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	85,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_38 (Illustration with priest with priest with pal branch) - image	.tif	35,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_39 (Partition with painting with naumachia) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	243	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_39 (Partition with painting with naumachia) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	54,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_4 (Frieze with dawning branch from achanthus tuft with pygmy and part of lower panel) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1230	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_4 (Frieze with dawning branch from achanthus tuft with pygmy and part of lower panel) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	170	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_40 (Illustration with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	124	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_40 (Illustration with landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	24,5	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_41 (Partition with painting with naumachia) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	348	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_41 (Partition with painting with naumachia) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	19,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_42 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1320	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_42 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	185	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_43 (Architectural view with painting with landscape, complete with base and frieze) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1800	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_43 (Architectural view with painting with landscape, complete with base and frieze) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	194	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_44 (Architctural view with painting with naumachia, complete with base and frieze) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1710	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_44 (Architctural view with painting with naumachia, complete with base and frieze) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	191	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_45 (Painting with architctural landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	177	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_45 (Painting with architectural landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	10,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_46 (Illustration with priestess with rotulo) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	45,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_46 (Illustration with priestess with rotulo) - image	.tif	156	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_47 (Painting with naumachia) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	179	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_47 (Painting with naumachia) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	11,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_48 (Illustration with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	44,8	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_48 (Illustration with landscape) - image	.tif	93	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_49 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	831	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_49 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - othophoto	.tif + .tfw	118	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_5 (Offering to the statue of Apocrate) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	598	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_5 (Offering to the statue of Apocrate) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	156	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_50 (Painting with landscape) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	225	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_50 (Painting with landscape) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	20,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_51 (Painting of landscape with peacocks) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	455	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_51 (Painting of landscape with peacocks) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	70,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_53 (Base with gorgoneion between lioness) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	158	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_53 (Base with gorgoneion between lioness) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	120	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_53b (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	317	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_53b (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	89,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_55 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	980	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_55 (Frieze with spiral branch crossed by animals) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	104	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_57 (Candelabra with priestess with situla and peacock) -raw	.CR3 + .jpg	27,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_57 (Candelabra with priestess with situla and peacock) - image	.tif	62,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_58 (Candelabra with priestess with tray for offerings) -raw	.CR3 + .jpg	29,8	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_58 (Candelabra with priestess with tray for offerings) - image	.tif	67,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_59 (Candelabra with priestess with tray for offerings) -raw	.CR3 + .jpg	28,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_59 (Candelabra with priestess with tray for offerings) - image	.tif	71,4	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_6 (Illustration with priest with palm branch and magpies) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	88,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_6 (Illustration with priest with palm branch and magpies) - image	.tif	142	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_60 (Candelabra with priestess with situla and cobra) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	26,5	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_60 (Candelabra with priestess with situla and cobra) - image	.tif	67,2	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_61 (Candelabra with priestess with stitula and crocodile) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	283	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_61 (Candelabra with priestess with stitula and crocodile) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	146	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_62 (Landscape with ceremony in honor of Osiris) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	345	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_62 (Landscape with ceremony in honor of Osiris) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	121	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_63 (Io welcomed by Isis at Canapo) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	415	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_63 (Io welcomed by Isis at Canapo) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	121	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_64 (Plinth with idra between androsfingi) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	259	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_64 (Plinth with idra between androsfingi) - orthofhoto	.tif + .tfw	68,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_65 (Plinth with icneumone and cobra) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	310	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_65 (Plinth with icneumone and cobra) - ortophoto	.tif + .tfw	62,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_66 (Sacred fence with tample, statuea, and square with trees, seen through and architectural scene) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	950	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_66 (Sacred fence with tample, statuea, and square with trees, seen through and architectural scene) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	174	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_67 (Landscape with sacred door and velum) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	491	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_67 (Landscape with sacred door and velum) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	262	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_68 (Rocky landscape with little temples, statue, fisherman and ibis) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	392	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_68 (Rocky landscape with little temples, statue, fisherman and ibis) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	177	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_69 (Io, Argo and Hermes) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	535	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_69 (Io, Argo and Hermes) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	1,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_7 (Illustration with architectural landscape) - RAW	.CR3 + .jpg	83,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_7 (Illustration with architectural landscape) - image	.tif	97,5	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_70 (Rocky landscape with little temple, sacred door and king-fisher) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	562	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_70 (Rocky landscape with little temple, sacred door and king-fisher) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	166	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_71 (Osiris-Serapide in throne between cobra beside a sicomoro with snake) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	503	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_71 (Osiris-Serapide in throne between cobra beside a sicomoro with snake) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	370	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_72 (Bes) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	220	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_72 (Bes) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	96	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_75 (Rolled up cobra, with flower of lotus on the head) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	129	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_75 (Rolled up cobra, with flower of lotus on the head) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	13,1	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_77 (Ibis) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	250	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_77 (Ibis) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	91,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_78 (Lion) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	170	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_78 (Lion) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	39,5	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_79 (Bull Api) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	506	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

1_79 (Bull Api) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	74,8	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_8 (Illustration with priest with cobra on crown of roses) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	87,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_8 (Illustration with priest with cobra on crown of roses) - image	.tif	31,5	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_9 (Illustration with still-life and goose) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	143	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
1_9 (Illustration with still-life and goose) - image	.tif + .tfw	52,8	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
2_1 (Inscription of Numerio Popidio Celsino) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	84	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
2_1 (Inscription of Numerio Popidio Celsino) - image	.tif	854	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Animali (Animals of Egypt's desert regions) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	376	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Animali (Animals of Egypt's desert regions) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	327	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Iside (Isis draws a boat bearing the body of Osiris through the marshlands of the Nile; below, serpents advance toward a mystic cista) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1050	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Iside (Isis draws a boat bearing the body of Osiris through the marshlands of the Nile; below, serpents advance toward a mystic cista) - photoplane	.tif + .tfw	296	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Photogrammetric acquisition of the scale model depicting the Temple of Isis – Room 80 of the MANN Museum in Naples - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	3500	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Scan of rooms 79, 81, 82, and 84 of the MANN Museum in Naples, displaying detached frescoes.	.bin + .e57	4860	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2, T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Berthault veduta tempio - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1260	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Berthault veduta tempio - photoplane	.tiff	338,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Nord - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	602	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3

Drawing - Casanova Parete Nord - photoplane	.tiff	81,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Nord (Porta) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	661	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Nord (Porta) - photoplane	.tiff	44,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Sud (Archi) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	611	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Sud (Archi) - photoplane	.tiff	36,6	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Est (nord) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1000	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Est (nord) - photoplane	.tiff	129,7	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Est (sud) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	925	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Casanova Parete Est (sud) - photoplane	.tiff	39,2	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. L a Vega Pianta Iseo - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	1050	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. L a Vega Pianta Iseo - photoplane	.tiff	165	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Iscrizione - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	213	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Dettaglio Porta 8 (ADS 894) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	38,9	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Dettaglio Purgatorium (ADS 913) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	314	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Dettaglio Facciata Naos (ADS 906) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	322	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Acquerello Ekklesiasterion (ADS 917) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	41,3	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. La Vega Sezioni Tempio (ADS 891) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg	195	MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. La Vega Lati Purgatorium - raw	.CR3 + .jpg		MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. La Vega Ingresso Cella - raw	.CR3 + .jpg		MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - F. La Vega Nicchia tempio (Dioniso) - raw	.CR3 + .jpg		MANN/CNR-ISPC	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Parete Ovest (sud) (ADS 899) - image	.jpg	36,8	MANN	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
Drawing - Oarete Ovest (nord) (ADS 901) - image	.jpg	0,152	MANN	Closed Access	M24	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3
		~50'000 (finetuning)				T4.1 T4.2 T4.3
scan of lenticular fim frames (doLCE 2.0)	.tif	2'700)	NTNU	Closed Access	M18	T5.3 T7.2 T8.4

XRF mapping data of V&A burse (T.40-1986)	.bcf + .tif + .jpg + .txt	4.000	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
XRF mapping data of V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954)	.bcf + .tif + .jpg + .txt	4.600	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
digital microscopy images of V&A burse (T.40-1986)	.jpg	6.000	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
digital microscopy images of V&A purse and pincushion (T.52-1954)	.jpg	491	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
3D photogrammetry files of V&A kimono	blend + .mtl + .obj	19.200	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
3D photogrammetry files of V&A dress	blend + .mtl + .obj	25.700	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Reflectance transformation imaging files of V&A burse, purse and pincushion	.jpg + .dzi + .ptm + .png	22.800	V&A	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	0.169	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A burse (T.40-1986) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt + .jpg	1.8	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A purse and pin cushion (T.52-1954) - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	0.307	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A purse and pin cushion (T.52-1954) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt + .jpg	3.17	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	0.124	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt	1.6	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A Kimono (FE.422-1992) - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	.hdr + .float + .pptx	1600	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	0.517	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Open Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt	5.6	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Open Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of V&A Kimono - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	.hdr + .float + .pptx	707.2	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Open Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2

V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	0.294	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt	2.2	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
V&A Dress (T.7-1926) - Hyperspectral imaging (HSI) data	.hdr + .float + .pptx	354.9	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of V&A Dress - colorimetry data	.xlsx + .jpg	2.9	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of V&A Dress - UV-Vis-NIR Reflectance (FORS) data	.txt	11.9	CNR- SCITEC/ISPC/UNIPG	Closed Access	M24	T3.1, T3.2
"Perceive Isis' Colours" - Evaluation data	.csv	0.322	CNR ISPC	Closed Access	M36	T6.2
"Perceive Isis' Colours" - GDPR and other policy from Evaluation	.pdf	0.277	CNR ISPC	Closed Access	M35	T6.2
Harold Taylor collection of autochromes (Maintainer Fraunhofer)	.jpg	27545	Fraunhofer	Closed access	M20	T4.1, T5.2
LenticularScans	.tiff	56422	NTNU	Closed access	M25	T4.1, T5.2
Mock-ups of polychromy - Multiangle reflectance data	.xlsx	435.4	NTNU	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of polychromy - Material Exchange file	.axf	2429.4	NTNU	Closed access	M30	T3.1, T3.2
Mock-ups of polychromy - Blender asset file	.blend	1783.9	NTNU	Closed access	M30	T3.1, T3.2
Erote_with_hare_inv6533-raw	.nef	1800	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Erote_with_hare_inv6533_pointcloud	.ply	10	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Erote_with_hare_inv6533-output-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	32,1	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Erote_with_hare_inv6533-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	11	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-raw-rgb	.cr2	6400	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-raw-uvl	.cr2	7200	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-raw-vil	.cr2	7200	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-processing-jpg-rgb	.jpg	3000	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-processing-jpg-uvl	.jpg	1800	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-processing-jpg-vil	.jpg	831	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-processing-workspace	.zep	873	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1

Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-packed	.blend	288,5	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	410	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-output-obj	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	42	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
Bikini_Venus_inv152798-video-reference	.mov	714	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T5.1
152798_microscope	.jpg	188	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
152798_fors	.Transmission	38	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
152798_xrf	.csv	36	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_without_legs_NOinv-raw	.cr2	5200	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_without_legs_NOinv-processing	.ply	20	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_without_legs_NOinv-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	39	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_without_legs_NOinv-output-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	15,8	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Microscope_Anadyomene_without_legs	.jpg	14	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
FORS_Anadyomene_without_legs	.Transmission	0,124	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
XRF_Anadyomene_without_legs	.csv	0,595	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
VIL_Anadyomene_without_legs	.jpg	4,7	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro_rawold	.arw	4900	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro_raw_v2	.cr2	3700	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro-processing-jpg	.jpg	2300	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Iside_RGB	.zep	249	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Iside_RGB_files	.3db	1900	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro-output	.blend	219	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro-output-gltf	.gltf	17,7	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isisi_with_sistro-output-textures	.png, .jpg, .bmp	1400	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
976_UVL	.tif	2500	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
976_vil	.tif	200	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2

976_Microscope	.jpg	106	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
976_XRF	.csv	8,4	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv111383-raw	.cr2	5000	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv111383-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	305	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2, T4.1
111383_Microscope	.bmp, .jpg	43	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
111383_FORs	.Transmission	0,407	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
111383_XRF	.csv, .pdz	0,202	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv126248-raw	.nef	2400	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv126248-processing	.jpg	1200	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv126248-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	73,8	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv126248-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	73,6	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_lseum_inv6298-rawold	.jpg	674	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_lseum_inv6298-raw	.cr2	1500	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_lseum_inv6298-processing	.ply	70,7	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_HighPoly	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	129,4	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_GLTF_optimised	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	17,5	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_UVL	.jpg	55	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_VIL	.jpg	22	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6928_Microscope	.jpg	14	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_XRF	.csv	2,8	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6298_FORs	.Transmission	0,125	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isis_Head_inv6290-raw	.cr2	1500	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isis_Head_inv6290-scanner-processing	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	694,2	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isis_head_pack	.blend	81,1	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Isis_Head_inv6290-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	86	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2

Isis_Head_inv6290-output-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	5	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
satyr_with_frog_inv6537-raw	.nef	1700	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
satyr_with_frog_inv6537-processing	.ply	10,6	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
satyr_with_frog_inv6537-output-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, .bin	139,8	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
satyr_with_frog_inv6537-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	9,8	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_crouching_inv114536-raw	.jpg	1200	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
114536_Microscope	.jpg	24,7	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
114536_RefPoints	.jpg, .bmp	7,4	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
114536_VIL	.jpg	4,3	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
114536_XRF	.csv	0,668	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
114536_FORs	.Transmission	0,251	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv6292-scanner	.a3d	<0,001	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv6292-scanner-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, . bin	21	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv6292-output-gltf	.gltf, .jpg, . bin	21	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Venus_Anadyomene_inv6292-output-obj	.obj, .jpg, .mtl	698	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6292_VIL	.cr2, .jpg	155	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6292_UVL	.jpg	105,6	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6292_Microscope	.bmp	91,8	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6292_FORs	.Transmission	0,818	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
6292_XRF	.csv	0,808	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Lovatelli Venus_inv109608-raw	.jpg	4001	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Lovatelli Venus_inv109608-raw	.cr2	4950	MANN/CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
109608_lovatelli_FORs	.Transmission	0,736	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
109608_lovatelli_MD	.jpg	16	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
109608_lovatelli_TR-FTIR	.jpg	24,8	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2

109608_lovatelli_UVL	.jpg	166	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
109608_lovatelli_VIL	.jpg, .cr2	528	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
109608_lovatelli_XRF	.csv, .pdz	0,754	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M18	T3.1, T3.2
Iseum_3D_survey	.blend	749	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-Altare_Purgatorium	.blend	64,4	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-Arch_Esterna	.blend	1,85	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-Iseum_portico_02bis	.blend	107	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-Purgatorium	.blend	29,4	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-References	.blend	1,33	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
iseum-Tempio	.blend	990	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-Anadiomene	.blend	406	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-ISIDE	.blend	436	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_01_SH_02	.blend	608	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_01_SH_02b	.blend	808	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_01_SH_03	.blend	413	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_02_SH_01	.blend	710	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_02_SH_06	.blend	639	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_03_SH_01	.blend	1002	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_03_SH_04	.blend	842	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_04_SH_01	.blend	559	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_05_SH_01	.blend	964	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_06_SH_01	.blend	966	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC_037_SH_01	.blend	1007	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC01_SH_04	.blend	457	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-SC01_SH_05	.blend	436	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1

modellivideo-TEMPIO	.blend	990	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
modellivideo-Scena1_Tempio11	.blend	1350	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH01	.exr	10200	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH02	.exr	10300	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH03	.exr	9930	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH04	.exr	12600	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH05	.exr	8100	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH05b	.exr	96700	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC01_SH06	.exr	10500	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC02_SH01	.exr	15100	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC02_SH02	.exr	5360	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC02_SH03	.exr	11900	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC02_SH07	.exr	8760	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC02_SH08	.exr	4320	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC03_SH01	.exr	10100	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC03_SH02	.exr	14700	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC03_SH03	.exr	172	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC03_SH04	.exr	6100	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC04_SH01	.exr	669	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC05_SH01	.exr	11100	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC05_SH02	.exr	324	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC06_SH01	.exr	829	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SC07_SH01	.exr	24600	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-SHOT P1.6	.exr	11200	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Video1-TheGiftsOfIstis-Sequenze-VenereAnadyomene	.exr	12200	CNR ISPC	Closed access	M30	T6.1

GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 1_Video Intro_20250904_EN	.mp4	353	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 2_Video Ricostruzione_20250905_EN	.mp4	207	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 3_Video Transizione_20250904_EN	.mp4	170	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 4_Video Task A-_20250904_EN	.mp4	159	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 5_Video Task B_20250904_EN	.mp4	149	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 6_Video Task C_20250904_EN	.mp4	79,4	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_PARTE 7_Video Rito finale_20250904_EN	.mp4	410	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskA_16-9	.mp4	34,2	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskA_9-16	.mp4	34,2	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskB_16-9	.mp4	71,5	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskB_9-16	.mp4	70	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskC_16-9	.mp4	70	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop preTaskC_9-16	.mp4	70	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Architetto_16-9	.mp4	70	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Architetto_9-16	.mp4	70	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Pittrice_16-9	.mp4	86,5	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Pittrice_9-16	.mp4	87	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Scultore_16-9	.mp4	86	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
GIFTS OF ISIS_Loop_Scultore_9-16	.mp4	85,5	CNR ISPC/NemaFX	Closed access	M30	T6.1
Prussian Blue Fading_MAXRF	.h5, .png	9300	CNR-SCITEC/ISPC, UNIPG, SMK	Closed access	M36	T3.1, T3.2
Prussian Blue Fading_VIS Hyperspectral Reflectance Spectroscopy	.jpg, .hdr	5600	CNR-SCITEC/ISPC, UNIPG, SMK	Closed access	M36	T3.1, T3.2